

**D2.3 Report on the
identification of relevant EU
projects and initiatives and the
procedure to identify potential
strategic interactions**

**WP2 Integrative Strategic
Research Agenda**

Responsible Partner: VISAVET-UCM

Contributing partners: RIVM, ANSES, CODA-
CERVA-VAR, BfR, SSI, IP, UoS, ISS, WbvR, INSA,
SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Procedure to identify EU-projects/initiatives and potential strategic interactions with One Health EJP

The WP2 “Integrative strategic research agenda” has three main objectives: 1) Identifying priority topics in the domains of foodborne zoonoses (FBZ), antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and emerging threats (ET); 2) Developing the strategic research agenda (SRA); and 3) Fostering strategic interactions with related EU projects and initiatives. In order to meet the third objective and fulfil Task 2.2 “Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives”, an analysis of the relevant EU-projects/initiatives and strategic interactions will be done.

Subtask 2.2.1. Identification of relevant EU-projects and initiatives

1. Search in the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS).

CORDIS is the European Commission's primary public repository and portal to disseminate information on all EU-funded research projects and their results. This website includes all public information held by the Commission, information to support communication and exploitation and comprehensive links to external sources such as open access publications and websites. CORDIS's principal aims are: a) to facilitate participation in Community research activities; b) to improve exploitation of research results, whilst focusing on sectors essential to Europe's competitiveness; and c) to promote the sharing of know-how in order to boost companies' innovation capacities, in particular by publishing the results of EU-financed research conducted under successive framework programmes, and the espousal of new technologies by society. CORDIS will be the main tool to identify projects relevant to the One Health EJP.

Moreover, the One Health **EJP partners** will collaborate in this task by providing information regarding related mainly EU projects and initiatives that they are aware of and that are not listed in the CORDIS database. The information will be sent to the Task 2.2. Leader (VISAVET-UCM, Dr. Lucía de Juan, dejuan@visavet.ucm.es).

The EU-projects/initiatives granted **during the lifespan of the One Health EJP** will be identified taking into account the main domains (FBZ, AMR and ET) and the topics included in the Strategic Research Agenda of the One Health EJP.

2. Create a One Health EJP database of relevant projects/initiatives.

The main information (name of the project, acronym, objectives, coordinator, period and financing entity) of each project/initiative will be recorded in a **descriptive sheet**. All the information on the different projects and initiatives will be compiled in a **database** that will be available to the One Health EJP Consortium through the password-protected area of the One Health EJP website (intranet/members' area). The database will be updated three times a year.

Moreover, for each project/initiative, the One Health EJP partners that are participating in the project/initiative will be identified to facilitate the interactions during the One Health EJP.

Subtask 2.2.2. Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives.

The scientific scope of the relevant projects/initiatives will be visualized in relation to the **One Health EJP matrix** consisting of three domains (FBZ, AMR, ET) and five themes (Analytical methods, Host-microbe interaction, Epidemiology, Risk assessment and socio-economic impact and intervention). The Project Management Team (PMT) will identify and select the relevant projects/initiatives for strategic interactions within the EJP One Health.

The strategic interactions will be effected by:

- Analysis of the **SRAs** of relevant EU project/initiative's and identification of synergies.
- **Active interaction** with the **coordinators** of relevant EU project/initiative's to identify common strategic objectives and potential synergies.
- Active interaction with the **Stakeholders Committee** (where some of the projects/initiatives are represented, ie. COMPARE, EFFORT and JPIAMR) together with the WP5 team and **External Scientific Advisory Board** (ESAB) to identify gaps and avoid redundancy (knowledge/fund).
- **Attendance to congresses or workshops.**
- **Cogwheel workshops (CW)** organized within WP4 to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration with other EU projects and initiatives.

Since the relevant EU projects/initiatives will be available to the whole EJP Consortium, all the strategic interactions should be informed to the coordinator and WP2 leader/deputy leader for reporting (M2.7).